

Indexing & Abstracting Services in Library- A Classical Approach

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ABSTRACT

Indexing & Abstracting plays a very important role in the retrieval and dissemination of information across the world. It is the main tool of information retrieval in the library. This paper highlights the various aspects about I&A for the library as well as researcher and investigator. The article gives an overview of I&A, its history, development of the concept, its functions and its impact towards the library and library professionals. The article enlightened librarians working in the library need to develop the skill and knowledge in the indexing and abstracting service to provide faster and easy access to the researcher in the short time possible.

KEYWORDS: *Indexing, abstracting, Information retrieval tools, library services*

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INTRODUCTION:

Indexing

Indexing has a vigorous part for retrieving information which is stored in the library. Its origin word is indexed in Latin and its meaning is 'to point out, to guide, to direct, to locate'. Indexing is for index all documents along with full bibliographical information, so that each document can be traced easily and faster. Indexing initially called cataloguing which is a very old method to classify the contents of items to assist their location.

1. The American National Standards Institute defines as, "a systematic guide to item contained in or concept from a collection (document, group of documents or set of objects). It is arranged in a known or stated order, usually different from that of the items or concepts within the collection itself."
2. British standards (BS 3700: 1964) defined as "a systematic guide to the text of any reading matter or to the contents of other collected documentary material, comprising a series of entries, with headings arranged in alphabetical or other chosen order and with references to show where each item indexed is located".

Abstracting

Abstract summarizes the entire study of any research paper in 250 Or 500 words. In Latin abstractus "drawn away", means 'to drag away, detach, pull away, divert'. It helps the reader to decide whether it is relevant or not to read the whole paper. It covers whole contextual information for the research paper. An abstract can be found as an advertisement of the whole product.

1. Lancaster (2003) defines an abstract as a brief but accurate representation of the contents of a document and he opines that an abstract is different from an extract, an annotation or summary.
2. Rowley (1996) defines an abstract as a concise and accurate representation of the content of a document in a style similar to that of the original document. She adds that an abstract covers all the main points made in the original document and usually follows the style and the arrangement of the parent document.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the concept and history of indexing & abstracting terms
- To know the types of indexing & abstracting services in the library

- To study the impact of indexing & abstracting in the library
- To find out the indexing & abstracting services is dying or not in the library.

INDEXING & ABSTRACTING SERVICES IN THE LIBRARY

Indexing & Abstracting (I&A) has a major role in retrieving the information in the library. It services faster and easy access to the knowledge resources which save the time of library users and guide them to appropriate sources of the information. I&A services have assisted researchers & investigators around the world with the easy access & retrieval of the knowledge resources in the library. These services provide the very easy access of the information sources to the library users; therefore, library users get satisfied by getting their required information within a short period of time.

Types of Indexing

Some types of indexing given below which requires specialised skills from indexers –

1. Bibliographical and database indexing – (provide records of journal article)
2. Genealogical indexing – (provide records of people's name and information about personal and family relationship)
3. Geographical indexing – (provide records of maps, atlases and cartographic materials)
4. Book indexing – (provide detailed contents of books)
5. Legal indexing – (provide legal materials by form of content)
6. Periodical and legal indexing – (give access to the contents of individual articles and other items in serialised publications)
7. Pictorial indexing – (provide record about pictures in collections of photographs, art works, videos and films)
8. Subject gateways - (provide records of new form of digital indexing)
9. Website and metadata indexing - (access to information on WWW)

Types of Abstracting

Types of abstracting includes as given below

1. Informative Abstracts – (It provide a summary on main concepts of the research, its methodology, conclusion and recommendation based on the research in 250 words approximately)
2. Descriptive Abstracts – (It provide a summary in 100 words in length with main focus of the study only, not the conclusion and recommendations)
3. Critical Abstracts – (It provides a summary in 450 words in length with a lot of analysis, points

about validity or reliability of the study. It often used in social science research)

4. Highlight Abstracts – (It is only to hook the reader's attention without providing information about the papers)

IMPACT OF INDEXING & ABSTRACTING IN THE LIBRARY

Indexing & Abstracting started in the 19th century as information storage and retrieval devices in the libraries and in other information centres. I&A has played a vital role in ensuring the flow of scholarly communication within the researchers and investigators in the library. These are knowledge organization tools which generally show the detailed and accurate path for the required information to the library users in the shortest time possible. Traditionally, information retrieval has been a challenge for the library professional, however, the availability of the Internet made literature searching directly available to widespread groups of researchers (Schatz, 1997). Everyday knowledge is generated in vast numbers and all knowledge and information are flowing together on the internet as well as manuals, the information retrieval tools are becoming absolutely critical. I&A has been coverage of the life and culture of academic organizations. So, the librarian has an important gate-keeping role in the libraries as indexer/abstractor. I&A are the big challenges for the librarian to classify and catalogue all the documents whether electronically or manually in the library. I&A requires technicality in producing and it involves time, money and effort to create an output. Nowadays I&A is the vital part of information retrieval sources around the world for researchers and investigators. For the librarian it is the big challenge to fulfil these needs for the library users. Bellow points which are affected to the librarian while facing I&A task –

- ICT already took over I&A
- Lack of knowledge and skills on practicing I&A
- Its time-consuming task specifically for a one-man librarian
- Users depend on mostly on the internet as faster & easy source for the information
- Need to develop the more knowledge and command
- Need to improve the necessary skills for I&A
- Librarians can't take this task as a burden or extra work in the library.
- Librarian has been taking it as a regular task of I&A

This implies that indexing is still a relevant task of a librarian in order to provide fast and easy access to information and content. Indexing and abstracting

helps in the timely distribution of information and the librarian always ensures that for every document be it electronically or manually are properly served to the library users. Most libraries do not properly maintain I&A records because librarians are not well trained in the technical skills for I&A. Overall, now each librarian is improving their knowledge and skill to prepare the Indexing and Abstracting sources for their users. Which obviously helps to save the time of their users. Indexing and Abstracting is not a dying practice in the library because now library professionals believe that I&A has a function to fulfil in the library. I&A is still being used as an aid to information retrieval therefore library professionals conveyed that I&A is still a very vigorous part of the library. It can really help users require information faster and easier. Information can now be easily gotten from the internet but still I&A has a vital role.

CONCLUSION

Indexing & Abstracting is the vital part of information retrieval source in the library which helps the users to the timely dissemination of the required information. The librarian should ensure that for every document classify and catalogued whether in digital or manually. Its need for I&A of such documents. It may be a phenomenal task for the librarian performing both the work of classification and cataloguing. Therefore, there is a need for some best trained staff in the library who have skills to serve in the indexing and abstracting, ability to categorize and classify, better equipped to have passion for accuracy, ability to read fast with good memory and wide general knowledge. This will help the library to provide the best service in retrieving and disseminating the information to the researcher and investigator.

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